

during the first 14 d of Sep.

Rice was directly sown on 30 Jun in rows spaced 20 cm. Sixty kg N/ha was topdressed in 3 splits: 24 kg N/ha at 15 d after germination (DG), 18 kg at 40 DG, and 18 kg at 55 DG.

Two levels of P as superphosphate and one level of K as muriate of potash were basally applied in a randomized block design with 3 replications (see table). A foliar spray of ZnSO₄ was also applied. The soil had 12.5 kg available P and 122 kg available K/ha.

Effect of P and K on yield of rainfed upland rice at Faizabad, U. P., India.

NPK (kg/ha)	Days to 50% heading	Panicles/m ²	Grains (× 10 ³ /m ²)	Sterility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Harvest index (%)	Yield (t/ha)
60-0-0	71.0	260.0	14.1	18.3	25.9	52.8	2.8
60-13-0	69.0	276.6	14.3	18.1	26.1	55.2	3.0
60-19.5-0	69.0	308.3	15.4	15.8	26.8	56.5	3.7
60-0-25	69.0	281.6	14.4	17.9	26.1	50.1	3.0
60-13-25	68.0	301.6	15.7	14.8	26.1	53.3	3.1
60-19.5-25	67.0	330.0	15.8	14.5	27.2	56.2	3.8
CD .05	1.2	25.2	0.7	ns	0.7	ns	0.1

ns = not significant.

Both P and K greatly increased yield. However, P was more beneficial.

The highest yield was obtained with 19.5 kg P and 25 kg K/ha. □

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Rice-based crop sequences for the Andaman Islands

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Monocrop rice is commonly grown Jun-Dec in the Andaman Islands, with most fields fallow during the Jan-Apr dry season. Different crops were evaluated in the 1984-85 and 1985-86 crop years following harvest of single or double rice crops. The soil of the test site is a clay loam. Short-duration IET4106 rice was grown May-Aug as first crop, followed by IR36 in Sep-Dec as a second crop. Rice received 90-60-40 kg NPK/ha and yielded 4.2-4.7 t/ha in the first crop and 1.9-2.6 t/ha in the second crop. Severe pest problems lowered IR36 yields.

Average grain yields of dry season crops and net return, 1984-86, Port Blair, India.

Crop sequence	Yield (t/ha)			Net return ^a (\$/ha)
	Crop 1	Crop 2	Crop 3	
Rice - fallow	4.6	—	—	348.75
Rice - sorghum	4.6	2.6	—	597.50
Rice - maize	4.7	3.4	—	733.33
Rice - sesamum	4.4	0.5	—	534.83
Rice - black gram	4.6	1.3	—	737.75
Rice - rice - sorghum	4.2	1.9	1.9	438.33
Rice - rice - maize	4.2	2.3	2.1	518.42
Rice - rice - sesamum	4.3	2.3	0.5	516.08
Rice - rice - black gram	4.4	2.6	1.1	714.17
Rice - rice - green gram	4.5	2.4	0.5	455.42

^a Based on 1984-86 local market rates.

Dry season crops were sown in Jan and harvested in Mar-Apr. Fertilizer applications were 60-40-30 kg NPK/ha for maize or sorghum, 40-30-30 for sesamum, and 20-40-25 for black gram or green gram.

Pulses, oilseeds, and cereals

performed well on residual soil moisture during the rice fallows (see table). This indicates that intensive cropping is feasible in the Andamans; cropping intensity could be increased by 200-300%. □

Fertilizer required for irrigated wheat in rice - wheat cropping pattern, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh

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The fertilizer requirement of wheat following rice was tested.

Medium-duration rice variety Kranti was used as test crop in kharif (wet season). Initial soil fertility is presented in Table 1. Rice received 80-23-25 kg NPK/ha and yielded 3.5-3.8 t/ha.

After rice harvest, wheat variety

Table 1. Soil fertility of experimental plots. Madhya Pradesh, India, 1981-83.

Character	1981-82	1982-83
pH	7.1	7.2
Organic C	0.6	0.5
Available N (kg/ha)	200	180
Available P (kg/ha)	15	14
Available K (kg/ha)	354	333